

A Technology-Based Intervention to Address Obesity in College Students

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Background

- At California State University, Dominguez Hills, it is estimated that 25% of students are overweight and 36% are obese
- Obesity is associated with cardiovascular disease, Type II diabetes, sleep apnea, arthritis, cancer, anxiety, and depression
- Providers at college health centers have limited time to adequately address obesity during office visits
- College students are avid users of technology

Purpose

- To evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of a technology-based weight loss and healthy lifestyle promotion intervention in a college setting

Methods

Pilot/Feasibility Study

- Setting: State university in Carson, CA
- Sample: N=7 (six female, one male)
- Intervention: 8-week program:
 - 1) health information posted on Instagram twice-weekly
 - 2) text-message support two times per week

Outcome Measures

- Weight, Body Mass Index (BMI)
- Score on the *Health Promoting Lifestyle Profile II (HPLP II)*
- Score on the author-developed *Benefits and Barriers Tool*

Conceptual Framework

Adapted Pender's Health Promotion Model

Results

Change in Weight from Baseline

Change in BMI from Baseline

HPLP II (Change after Intervention)

Benefits and Barriers Scores (Change after Intervention)

Challenges/Limitations

- Unable to obtain permission to send out mass email to student body regarding study so had to rely only on posters for recruitment
- Small sample size
- Only one male enrolled
- Short duration of intervention

Discussion

- Despite short duration of the intervention, 57% of participants lost weight and lowered their BMI
- Overall improvement in health promoting lifestyle behaviors was seen
- Increased perceived benefits and decreased perceived barriers to making lifestyle changes
- Overall average program satisfaction score was 4, on a 5-point Likert scale
- Some participants would have liked to have in-person meetings in addition to online education and text-messaging support

Nursing Practice Implications

- Program is inexpensive, easy to administer, and well-received by students
- This program could be adapted to be administered by other healthcare providers
- Additional research with a larger sample size to confirm the preliminary findings of this study
- Strategies for increasing the number of participants (especially males) are needed
- Contact campbellchris123@msn.com for more information